

ISic0701

I.Sicily inscription 0701

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2006.04

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Centuripae

Place of origin (modern)

Centuripe

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Centuripe, Museo Archeologico Regionale di Centuripe, inventory KA859

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Rustia G(ai)
2. f(ilia) Festia ann(os)
3. XIII pia sal(ve)

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644895

Bibliography

Libertini, G 1949. Iscrizioni Centuripine. *Siculorum Gymnasium*. 2: 91-97. At 97 no.4 fig.5

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